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MS Received: 18.05.2024; MS Revised:15.06.2024; MS Accepted:16.06.2024

MS 3212

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL PROCESS ENGINEERING,,)

Abstract

The process parameters for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel were optimized using response surface methodology. Sugar syrup temperature (30-50 °C), syrup concentration (10-40 °Brix) and duration of osmosis (60-240 min) were the factors investigated with respect to water loss (WL) and sugar gain (SG). The solution to sample ratio of 5/1 (w/w) was used. The Box- Behnken design of three variables and three levels including 17 experiments formed by 5 central points was used for optimizing input parameters. With respect to water loss and solid gain, the linear, quadratic and interaction effects of three variables were analysed. For each response, second order polynomial models were developed using multiple regression analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to check the adequacy and accuracy of the fitted models. The response surfaces and contour maps showing the interaction of process variables were constructed. The optimum operating conditions were found to be syrup temperature of 31.44 °C, syrup concentration of 25.35°Brix and osmosis time of 128.73 min. At this optimum point, water loss and sugar gain were predicted to be 39.69 % and 4.45 % respectively.

Key words – Osmotic dehydration, optimization, response surface method, aloe vera

Introduction

Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis* Miller) is a member of the family Liliaceae, which comprises more than 360 different species found in the arid regions of Africa, Asia, Europe and the Americas. It is widely used as a natural treatment and alternative therapy for various types of diseases and several studies have suggested the healing, cosmetic and nutritional benefits of aloe vera (Chang et al., 2006; Vega, et al., 2007).

The parenchyma cells of aloe vera leaves contain a transparent mucilaginous jelly that is referred to as aloe vera gel consisting of long chain polysaccharides. The gel is a colourless, odourless and hydrocolloid with several natural beneficial substances (Grindlay and Reynolds, 1986). Aloe vera gel, like most natural juices from fruit and vegetable, is an unstable product when extracted and is subject to discolouration and spoilage from contamination by microorganisms (Coats, 1979).

Unfortunately, because of improper processing procedure, many of the so called aloe products contain very little or virtually no active ingredients (Ramachandra and Rao, 2006). In view of the known wide spectrum of biological activities possessed by the leaves of the aloe vera plant and its wide spread use, it has become very important to evolve a better method of preservation for increasing the shelf life besides maintaining the quality of aloe vera gel and this can be achieved by some type of processing e.g. heating, dehydration (Chang, et al., 2006). The main purpose of drying products is to allow longer periods of storage, minimize packaging requirements and reduce shipping weights (Okos, et al., 1992).

Osmotic dehydration is widely used to remove part of the water content of fruit to obtain a product of intermediate moisture or as a pre-treatment before further processing (Lenart, 1996; Torreggiani & Bertolo, 2004). Osmotic dehydration is also used to treat fresh produce before further drying to improve sensory, functional and even nutritional properties. The shelf life quality of the final product is better than without such treatment due to the increase in sugar/acid ratio, the improvement in texture and the stability of the colour pigment during storage. Osmotic dehydration combined with other drying technologies provides an opportunity to produce novel shelf stable types of high quality pineapple products for the local as well as export market (Peiro, et al., 2003; Rastogi, et al., 2002).

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a statistical procedure frequently used for optimization studies. It uses quantitative data from an appropriate experimental design to determine and simultaneously solve multivariate problems. Equations describe the effect of test variables on responses, determine interrelationships among test variables and represent the combined effect of all test

variables in any response. This approach enables an experimenter to make efficient exploration of a process or system (Madamba, 2002). Therefore, RSM has been frequently used in the optimization of food processes (Shi, et al., 2008; Altan, et al., 2008).

Limited efforts have so far been made to process aloe vera into dehydrated product. An expanding interest currently exists for osmo-convective dehydrated aloe vera in the domestic and world market. No attempt has been made to optimize the osmotic process parameters for aloe vera. The purpose of the present work was to study the effect of osmotic process parameters viz. syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis on water loss and solid gain and to optimize these parameters for developing higher quality finished product.

Materials and methods**Materials Selection and Sample Preparation**

A widely grown '*Aloe barbadensis* Miller' variety of aloe vera was selected for all the experiments. The two years old and matured aloe vera leaves were and thoroughly washed under tap water to remove adhering impurities. Aloin (a yellow colour liquid) which is laxative or purgative if consumed in large amount was extracted by cutting the base of the leaves and allowing them to drain vertically for 1 hour. The epidermis was separated from gel (pulp) and gel was then cut into 10 x 10 x 10 mm ± 1 cubes with the help of sharp stainless steel cutter. Sugar syrups of various concentrations were prepared by dissolving required amount of sugar in distilled water.

Osmotic dehydration of aloe vera cubes

The initial moisture content of raw and aloe vera cubes was determined by oven drying as described by Ranganna (2000). The cubes of 1 cm size were osmotically dehydrated using sugar syrup to fruit ratio of 5:1 in the constant temperature water bath. The syrup was manually stirred at regular intervals to maintain uniform temperature. At pre-decided time the samples were removed from syrup and placed on tissue paper for 5 min to eliminate excess syrup from the surface. The samples were weighed and their moisture contents determined. The water loss and sugar gain were also calculated. The three independent process parameters, its coded and decoded values used in the study are given in Table 1.

Optimization of input parameters for osmotic dehydration

The process parameters (sugar syrup concentration, syrup temperature and duration of osmosis) were optimized for maximum of water loss and optimum sugar gain (4.59%). This optimum sugar gain was decided by taking sensory evaluation of osmo-convectively dried aloe vera samples having different sugar gain levels.

Design of experiments

The method of response surfaces deals with the problem of seeking the conditions of an experiment, which are optimal, *i.e.*, most desirable. The techniques applied here are standard techniques, which have been described in detail by Myers (1971). The Box- Behnken design of three variables and three levels including 17 experiments formed by 5 central points was used (Box and Behnken, 1960). The osmotic dehydration was assumed to be affected by three independent variables (regressor or factors), r_i , *viz.*, sugar syrup temperature (T), sugar syrup concentration (C) and duration of osmosis (θ). The experimental design of independent parameters and layout are shown in Tables 1 for these three levels and three variables under the Response Surface Methodology (Mullen and Ennis, 1979; Floros and Chinnan, 1987). The dependent variables, also referred as responses, Y_k (*i.e.*, the percentage of water loss and sugar gain) were measured experimentally.

The second order polynomial equation of the following form was assumed to relate the response, with independent process parameters as

$$Y_k = \beta_{ko} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_{ki}x_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_{kii}x_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=i+1}^3 \beta_{kij}x_ix_j \quad \dots 1$$

Where, Y_k is response (*i. e.* Water loss or sugar gain) β_{ko} , β_{ki} , β_{kii} and β_{kij} are constant coefficients and x_i and x_j are the coded independent variables that are linearly related to T, C and θ .

Hence, Eqn. (1) takes the following form as

$$Y_k = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_{11}x_1^2 + \beta_{22}x_2^2 + \beta_{33}x_3^2 + \beta_{12}x_1x_2 + \beta_{13}x_1x_3 + \beta_{23}x_2x_3 \quad \dots 2$$

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was applied to the experimental data using the package, Design- Expert version 8.0.4.1 (Statease Inc, Minneapolis, USA, Trial version).

Table 1 Experimental layout for 3 variables and 3 levels (coded) response surface analysis

Treatment no.	Syrup temperature, °C	Syrup concentration, °Brix	Duration of osmosis, min
	x_1	x_2	x_3
1	1(50)	1(40)	0(150)
2	1(50)	-1(10)	0(150)
3	-1(30)	1(40)	0(150)
4	-1(30)	-1(10)	0(150)
5	1(50)	0(25)	1(240)
6	1(50)	0(25)	-1(60)
7	-1(30)	0(25)	1(240)
8	-1(30)	0(25)	-1(60)
9	0(40)	1(40)	1(240)
10	0(40)	1(40)	-1(60)
11	0(40)	-1(10)	1(240)
12	0(40)	-1(10)	-1(60)
13	0(40)	0(25)	0(150)
14	0(40)	0(25)	0(150)
15	0(40)	0(25)	0(150)
16	0(40)	0(25)	0(150)
17	0(40)	0(25)	0(150)

Numerical optimization

Numerical optimization technique of the Design-Expert software was used for simultaneous optimization of the multiple responses. The desired goals for each factor and response were chosen. All the independent factors (T, C and θ) were kept minimized from economical point of view while the responses *viz.* water loss was kept maximized and sugar gain was kept targeted.

Graphical optimization

Graphical optimization was also carried out for the process parameters for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel for obtaining the best product. For graphical optimization, super imposition of contour plots for all responses was done with respect to process variables using Design-Expert software. The superimposed contours of all responses for syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis and their intersection zone for maximum water loss and targeted sugar gain indicated the ranges of variables, which could be

considered as the optimum range for best product quality in terms of responses. The optimum combinations of product and process variables for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel were derived by averaging those ranges of variables.

Verification of Optimum Responses

The optimum responses were verified by conducting the osmotic dehydration experiment under optimum conditions. The responses such as water loss and sugar gain at optimum processing conditions were compared to the values predicted by the mathematical model.

Results and discussion

Effect of variables on water loss

The initial moisture content of aloe vera gel samples was in the range of 98.13-99.16 % (wb) which was reduced to 86.24- 96.57 % after osmotic dehydration in various experiments causing WL and SG of 29.63 – 50.97 % and 0.65 – 6.25 % respectively (Table 2).

Table 2 Experimental data for water loss and sugar gain under different treatment conditions

S. No.	Syrup temp., °C	Syrup conc., °Brix	Duration of osmosis, min	Initial mass, g	Final mass, g	IMC (wb), %	FMC (wb), %	Water loss, %	Sugar gain, %
1	50	40	150	50.29	27.86	98.62	86.24	50.85	6.25
2	50	10	150	50.33	30.61	99.01	95.11	41.17	1.98
3	30	40	150	50.24	30.14	98.61	89.47	44.93	4.93

4	30	10	150	50.37	33.88	98.80	96.54	33.87	1.13
5	50	25	240	50.28	28.10	98.91	88.03	49.71	5.60
6	50	25	60	50.19	32.92	98.91	91.73	38.74	4.33
7	30	25	240	50.38	31.51	98.13	89.78	41.98	4.52
8	30	25	60	50.12	35.03	98.13	92.56	33.43	3.33
9	40	40	240	50.69	27.81	99.16	87.82	50.97	5.84
10	40	40	60	50.77	32.54	99.16	92.00	40.19	4.29
11	40	10	240	50.46	32.26	98.22	94.00	38.13	2.05
12	40	10	60	50.10	35.58	98.22	96.57	29.63	0.65
13	40	25	150	50.72	31.39	98.27	89.21	43.06	4.95
14	40	25	150	50.40	31.05	98.27	88.91	43.50	5.10
15	40	25	150	50.41	31.14	98.27	88.95	43.32	5.10
16	40	25	150	50.39	31.11	98.27	88.48	43.64	5.38
17	40	25	150	50.35	31.09	98.27	88.39	43.69	5.44

A second order polynomial equation [Eqn. (2)] was fitted with the experimental data presented in Table 2 for water loss. Eqn. (3) gives the predicted water loss, percent as a function of syrup temperature (x_1), concentration (x_2) and duration of osmosis (x_3) expressed in coded form. This equation was obtained using step-down regression method where factors with F-values less than one were rejected as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1967). The data for water loss were analysed for stepwise regression analyses as shown in Table 3. The quadratic model was fitted to the experimental data (Table 3).

The R^2 value was 0.9966 showing good fit of model to the data. The model F value of 377.23 implies that the model is significant ($P < 0.01$). The linear terms (T, C & θ) are significant ($P < 0.01$). The lack of fit F value was non-significant which indicates that the developed model was adequate for predicting the response. Moreover, the predicted R^2 of 0.9831 was in reasonable agreement with adjusted R^2 of 0.9940. This revealed that the non-significant terms have not been included in the model. Therefore, this model could be used to navigate the design space.

Table 3 Analysis of variance for water loss during osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of squares	F value
Model	557.27	7	79.61	377.23**
T	86.12	1	86.12	408.09**
C	243.81	1	243.81	1155.30**
θ	188.13	1	188.13	891.45**
T θ	1.47	1	1.47	6.94*
C θ	1.32	1	1.32	6.24*
C^2	3.99	1	3.99	18.92**
θ^2	31.08	1	31.08	147.26**
Residual	1.90	9	0.21	
Lack of Fit	1.63	5	0.33	4.90 ^{NS}
Pure Error	0.27	4	0.067	
Cor Total	559.17	16		
R^2	0.9966			
Adj. R^2	0.9940			
Pred. R^2	0.9831			
C.V. %	1.10			
SD	0.46			

** Significant at 1 % Level

* Significant at 5 % Level

NS - Non significant

The result of analysis of variance of Eqn (3) indicated that the linear terms of syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis were highly significant at 1 % level (Table 3). The presence of quadratic terms of concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis indicated curvilinear nature of response surface. The quadratic terms of concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis were also highly significant at 1 per cent level while interaction terms of temperature of syrup and duration of osmosis as well as concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis were significant at 5 per cent level.

The comparative effect of each factor on water loss would be observed by the F values in the ANOVA (Tables 3) and by the magnitudes of coefficients of the coded variables. The F values indicated that concentration of syrup was the most influencing factor followed by duration of osmosis and temperature of syrup was least effective over water loss. The regression equation describing the effects of process variables on water loss in terms of coded values of variable is given as

$$WL = 43.55 + 3.28x_1 + 5.52x_2 + 4.85x_3 + 0.61x_1x_3 + 0.57x_2x_3 - 0.97x_1^2 - 2.71x_2^2 - 3.35x_3^2 - 4.32x_1x_2 - 3.35x_1x_3 - 3.35x_2x_3$$

...3

and in terms of decoded (actual) values of variable is given as

$$WL = 8.53 + 0.23T + 0.52C + 0.12\theta + 6.73 \times 10^{-4}T\theta + 4.25 \times 10^{-4}C\theta - 4.32 \times 10^{-3}T^2 - 3.35 \times 10^{-4}C^2 - 3.35 \times 10^{-4}\theta^2$$

...4

The linear positive terms [Eqn. (3)] indicated that water loss increased with increase in syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis. The presence of positive interaction terms between syrup temperature and duration of osmosis as well as syrup concentration and duration of osmosis indicated that increase in their levels increased water loss. The negative values of quadratic terms of syrup concentration and duration of osmosis indicated that higher values of these variables further reduced water loss.

To visualize the combined effect of two variables on the water loss, the response surface and contour plots (Fig 1 A and B) were generated for the fitted model as a function of two variables while keeping third variable at its central value. The water loss increased rapidly in the early stages of osmosis (Fig 1 B), after which the rate of water loss from aloe vera gel sample into sugar syrup gradually slowed down with time. Rapid removal of water in early stages of osmosis has been reported for apple (Conway, *et al.*, 1983), carrots (Uddin, *et al.*, 2004), etc. Higher temperatures seem to promote faster water loss through swelling and plasticizing of cell membranes as well as the better water transfer characteristics on the product surface due to lower viscosity of the osmotic medium (Conteras and Smyral, 1981; Uddin, *et al.*, 2004). Water loss increased with concentration of syrup as well as with duration of osmosis also over the entire osmotic dehydration process.

(A) At 150 min duration of osmosis

(B) At 25°Brix syrup concentration

Fig 1 The contour and response surface showing the effect of temperature, concentration and duration on water loss during osmotic dehydration

Effect of variables on sugar gain

The sugar gain during the osmotic dehydration was found to be dependent on the syrup temperature, concentration and duration of osmosis.

A second order polynomial equation [Eqn. (2)] was fitted with the experimental data presented in Table 3. Eqn. (5) gives the predicted sugar gain, percent as a function of syrup temperature (x_1), concentration (x_2) and duration of osmosis (x_3) expressed in coded form. The quadratic model was fitted to the experimental data for sugar gain (Table 2) and the data for sugar gain were analyzed for

stepwise regression analysis as shown in Table 4. The R^2 value was found to be 0.9932 showing good fit of model to the data. The model F value of 243.48 implies that the model is significant ($P < 0.01$). The linear terms (T, C and θ) are significant ($P < 0.01$). The lack of fit F value was non-significant, which indicates that the developed model was adequate for predicting the response. Moreover the predicted R^2 was in reasonable agreement with adjusted R^2 . This revealed that the non-significant terms have not been included in the model. Therefore this model could be used to navigate the design space.

Table 4 Analysis of variance for sugar gain during osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of squares	F value
Model	46.56	6	7.76	243.48**
T	2.25	1	2.25	70.75**
C	29.97	1	29.97	940.43**
θ	3.66	1	3.66	114.86**
T^2	0.16	1	0.16	4.93 ^{NS}
C^2	8.59	1	8.59	269.55**
θ^2	1.31	1	1.31	41.08**

Residual	0.32	10	0.032	
Lack of Fit	0.14	6	0.024	0.55 ^{NS}
Pure Error	0.17	4	0.044	
Cor Total	46.88	16		
R ²	0.9932			
Adj. R ²	0.9891			
Pred. R ²	0.9819			
C.V. %	4.28			
SD	0.18			

** Significant at 1% level

NS - Non significant

The result of analysis of variance indicated that the linear terms of syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis were highly significant at 1 per cent level (Table 4). The presence of quadratic terms of concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis indicated curvilinear nature of response surface. The quadratic terms of concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis were also highly significant at 1 per cent level while quadratic term of temperature was non significant.

The comparative effect of each factor on sugar gain could be observed by F values in the ANOVA (Table 4) and by the magnitudes of the coded variables. The F values indicated that concentration of syrup was the most influencing factor followed by duration of osmosis and temperature of syrup was least effective over sugar gain.

The regression equation describing the effects of process variables on sugar gain in terms of coded values of variables is given as

$$SG = 5.19 + 0.53x_1 + 1.94x_2 + 0.68x_3 - 0.19x_1^2 - 1.43x_2^2 - 0.56x_3^2$$

$$\dots 5$$

$$(R^2 = 0.9932)$$

and in terms of decoded (actual) values,

$$SG = -9.89 + 0.21T + 0.45C + 0.03\theta - 1.93 \times 10^{-3} T^2 - 6.35 \times 10^{-3} C^2 - 6.89 \times 10^{-5} \theta^2$$

The linear positive terms [Eqn. (5)] indicated that sugar gain increased with increase in syrup temperature, syrup concentration and duration of osmosis. The negative values of quadratic terms of temperature of syrup, concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis indicated that higher values of these variables further reduced sugar gain.

To visualize the combined effect of two variables on the sugar gain, the response surface and contour plots (Fig 2 A and B) were generated for the fitted model as a function of two variables while keeping third variable at its central value.

The sugar gain increased rapidly in the early stages of osmosis after which the rate of sugar gain from sugar syrup to aloe vera gel sample slowed down with time.

The sugar gain was found to increase with temperature. As it was explained for water loss, temperature has an effect on the cell membrane permeability that could allow solute to enter by loosing its selectivity. Decrease of solution viscosity at higher temperature may influence sugar gain due to fact that lower viscosity decreases the

resistance to diffusion of solutes into the sample (food product) tissue.

Increased concentration of the sugar syrup also led to increase in sugar gain probably due to an increase of osmotic pressure gradient and consequent loss of functionality of cell plasmatic membrane that allows solute to enter.

It was observed from these figures (Fig. 1 & 2) that the moisture loss as well as the solid gain increased non linearly with time at all concentrations. Both moisture loss and solid gain were faster in the initial period of osmosis and then the rate decreased. This was because osmotic driving potential for moisture as well solid transfer will keep on decreasing with time as the moisture keeps moving from sample to solution and the solids from solution to sample. Further progressive solid uptake would result in the formation of high solid sub surface layer, which would interface with the concentration gradients across the sample solution interface and would set as barrier against removal of water and uptake of solid (Hawkes and Flink, 1978). Besides, rapid loss of water and uptake of solids near the surface in the beginning may result in structural changes leading to compaction of this surface layers and increased mass transfer resistance for water and solids (Lenart and Flink, 1984). Similar trends have been reported for other fruits and vegetables during osmosis (Coway, *et al.*, 1983; Lazarides, *et al.*, 1995; Erketin and Cakaloz, 1996; Ghosh, 2002).

Optimization of osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

Numerical and graphical multiresponse optimization technique was adapted to determine the workable optimum conditions for the osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel. To perform this operation, Design expert programme version 8.0.4.1 of the STAT-EASE software (Statease Inc, Minneapolis, USA, Trial version), was used for simultaneous optimization of the multiple responses.

The constraints were set such that the selected variables (T, C and θ) would be minimum from economical point of view for the most important product attribute and close to the optimum for the others (Jain, *et al.*, 2011). The main criteria for constraints optimization were maximum possible water loss and targeted sugar gain of 4.59 percent as most important quality (sweetness attribute).

Table 5 shows the software generated optimum conditions of independent variables with the predicted values of responses.

(B) At 25 °Brix syrup concentration

Fig 2 The contour response surface showing the effect of temperature, concentration and duration on sugar gain during osmotic dehydration

Table 5 Solutions generated by the software for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

No.	Temperature, °C	Concentration, °Brix	Duration, min	Water loss, %	Sugar gain, %
1	31.44	25.35	128.73	39.69	4.45*

*Selected

(A) At duration of osmosis = 128.73 min

(B) At concentration of syrup = 25.35 °Brix

Fig 3 Superimposed contours for water loss (%) and sugar gain (%) for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel at varying (A) concentration of syrup and temperature of syrup and (B) concentration of syrup and duration of osmosis

The superimposed contours of all responses for C and T (Fig. 3 A) and C and θ (Fig. 3 B) and their intersection zone for maximum water loss and targeted sugar gain (4.59%) indicated the ranges of variables which could be considered as the optimum range for best product quality. The ranges of optimum values of process variables obtained from the superimposed contours, are as follows,

Temperature of syrup (T) : 30-38 °C

Table 6 Predicted and experimental values of response at optimum process conditions for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

Response	Predicted value	*Experimental value (\pm SD)	C.V., %
Water loss, %	39.69	40.72(\pm 1.53)	3.76
Sugar gain, %	4.45	4.68(\pm 0.368)	7.85

* Average of three replications

The observed experimental values (mean of 3 experiments) and values predicted by the equations of the model are presented in Table 6. The experimental values were found to be very close to the predicted values for water loss and sugar gain, with the value of C.V. as 3.76 percent and 7.85 percent respectively. Therefore, it could be concluded from above discussion that model Eqns. (3) and (5) are quite adequate to assess the behavior of the osmotic dehydration.

Conclusion

Concentration of syrup was the most influencing factor followed by duration of osmosis and temperature of syrup was least effective over water loss and sugar gain. The optimal conditions for maximum water loss and optimum sugar gain correspond to syrup temperature of 31.44 °C, syrup concentration of 25.35 °Brix and duration of osmosis of 128.73 min in order to obtain water loss of 39.69 % and sugar gain of 4.45 %. The fitted mathematical models were quite adequate to assess the behavior of the osmotic dehydration.

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Concentration of syrup (C) : 18-29 °Brix
Duration of osmosis (θ) : 77-150 min

Verification of the model for osmotic dehydration of aloe vera gel

Osmotic dehydration experiments were conducted at the optimum process conditions ($x_1 = 31$ °C, $x_2 = 25$ °Brix and $x_3 = 29$ min) for testing the adequacy of model equations for predicting the response values.

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